

PRODUCTION STUDY OF CARBON FIBER WOVEN FABRIC/PA6 COMPOSITE SHEET USING PA6 SOLUTION

O. Ishida^{1*}, W. Okumura², M. Kimizu², K. Uzawa¹ and I. Kimpara¹

¹ Kanazawa Institute of Technology, 3-1 Yatsukaho, Hakusan 924-0838, Japan,
Email: o-ishida@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

² Industrial Research Institute of Ishikawa, 2-1 Kuratsuki, Kanazawa 920-8203, Japan

Keywords: Thermoplastic composite; Carbon fiber woven fabric; Solution method

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) is known as attractive material for automobile and industry parts, because it has the possibility to realize the high volume production. The thermoplastic composite sheet produced from carbon fiber woven fabric and polyamide 6 (PA6) is the development target in this study. It is useful due to the high strength and heat resistance. A common method to produce thermoplastic composite sheet is film stacking. But this has difficulty in impregnating carbon fiber bundles with resin due to the resin's high melt viscosity. Usually this process needs high pressure and long time, so that is the main problem for the manufacturing technology. One measure to solve this problem is the solution method. In this method, carbon fiber fabrics are impregnated with matrix resin solution which is low viscosity, so that good impregnation can be easily obtained. Polyamide has high solvent resistance and can't be solved in common solvents, but solved in the mixture of calcium chloride dehydrates (CaCl₂) and methanol. This solvent is hopeful for the manufacturing process due to the low cost and safety. In recent our study we used this solution to produce CF/PA6 composite and found the effectiveness to obtain good impregnation. In this study the composite production process using this method was investigated in detail by analysing the effects of the solution concentrations and the compression moulding time on the composite quality.

1 INTRODUCTION

CFRTP is a promising material for automobile and industrial parts because it has the possibility to realize the high volume production. Thermoplastic composite sheet is an intermediate material, from which parts can be produced using thermoforming process. The composite sheet composed of carbon fiber woven fabrics and PA6 resin can be a suitable material for the target because of the high strength and high thermal resistance.

Film stacking is a common method to produce thermoplastic composite. The normal procedure is as follows. Carbon fiber woven fabrics and thermoplastic resin films are stacked alternately, and then hot-pressed in order to impregnate carbon fiber bundles with resin, and cooled down to solidify the composite. This method has a difficulty in impregnating carbon fiber bundles with thermoplastic resin which has high melt viscosity, so that usually this process needs high pressure and long time, and this is a critical problem for manufacturing process.

One of the measures to solve this problem is to decrease thermoplastic resin viscosity. For example, the method to use liquid monomer for polyamide has been reported [1, 2], in this method, liquid monomer was injected into carbon fiber fabric and polymerized in the mould. On the other hand, the method to use the solution in which matrix resin is dissolved is another effective way. PA6 has high chemical resistance and can't be solved in common solvents except for formic acid, phenol, etc. But it's known that it can be solved in the mixture of calcium chloride (CaCl₂) and methanol [3]. This solvent is safe, not expensive and easy to be applied in manufacturing process, so that it is hopeful for high volume production. In recent our study, we investigated the process to impregnate carbon fiber woven fabric with PA6 resin solution and then produced CF/ PA6 composite using film stacking method. And this method was found to effective to obtain good impregnation quality of the composite [4].

The aim of this study is to investigate the fabrication process of CF/PA6 composite using the solution method in detail, by analysing the effects of the solution concentrations and the compression moulding time on the composite quality.

2 EXPERIMENTALS

2.1 Materials

In this study, carbon fiber plain woven fabric (T700SC-12K, 3.27yarns/25mm, 200g/cm², Toray co., ltd.), and PA6 resin pellet ('Amilan', CM1021, MFR=24 (270°C), Toray co., ltd.) were used.

2.2 Impregnation process of carbon fiber woven fabric using PA6 solution

First, the mixture of calcium chloride dihydrate and methanol (CaCl₂/the mixture concentration of 30wt%) was prepared. And PA6 pellet was dissolved into the mixture with 2.5, 5, 7.5wt%, respectively. The solution's viscosity increased as the solution concentration increased.

Then, the solution impregnation process of carbon fiber woven fabric was performed as follows. First, carbon woven fiber fabric was dipped in the solution and impregnated with resin solution, and then dried in the air to volatilize methanol. And the fabric was washed in water for 15 min to remove CaCl₂, and dried again. Finally, the carbon fiber woven fabric impregnated with PA6 resin was obtained.

In order to evaluate the case of not using solution impregnation process, carbon fiber woven fabrics treated with methanol were also prepared. Because in the solution impregnation process, the sizing agent on carbon fiber surface might be partly removed by methanol in the solution, so that the process to make the similar chemical condition of carbon fibers surface for all the specimens was performed.

The cross sections of these carbon fiber woven fabrics were analysed using Energy dispersive X ray spectrometry (EDX) (EX-250, Horiba Co., Ltd.) in order to evaluate the remaining contents of Ca and Cl elements originated from CaCl₂ in the solution.

2.3 Compression molding process

The compression molding process was performed as follows. First, the carbon fiber woven fabric impregnated with PA6 resin and PA6 resin films were stacked up alternately in 0°/90°. The stacking layers were 8 of carbon fiber woven fabrics and 9 of PA6 resin films, and the size of the materials was 10 x 10 cm. These PA6 films were produced from PA6 resin pellet using a hot press, and the film's thicknesses were adjusted to 60-100 μm according to the resin amounts in the carbon fiber woven fabrics given by solution impregnation process in order to obtain the same fiber volume fraction (V_f) of all the final molded composites (V_f =around 50%).

Next, the compression molding process with heat and cool method was performed as follows. The diagram is shown in Fig. 1. The stacked materials were pre-heated at 270°C (heat plate temperature) for 10 min, and compressed at 10 MPa for 2.5 min, and then cooled down under 80°C, and finally composite material was obtained. In addition, the holding time of temperature and pressure was changed to 10 and 20 min to evaluate the relationship between the molding time and the composite property.

Fig. 1 Compression molding diagram

2.4 Evaluations of the composites

The produced composites were evaluated as following methods. First, the cross sections were polished and then observed with optical microscope in order to evaluate the impregnation quality. And the V_f and void contents were measured according to JIS k 7075 by burning method.

Then, 3 points bending test was conducted using a universal test machine (AG-XPlus, Simazu Co., Ltd.) according to JIS K 7074. The size of specimens was 15 mm width, 80 mm span length, and the test speed was 5 mm/min.

And a preliminary investigation for the subsequent thermoforming process was conducted. The composite sheets (produced by the molding time of 20 min as described before) were heated on the mold at 270°C for 5 min and then cooled down with no pressure. And the cross section was observed with optical microscope to evaluate the voids that appeared inside the composite during the heating process.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Results of PA6 solution impregnation process

The amounts of PA6 resins in the carbon fiber woven fabrics given by the solution impregnation process (resin volume/the sum volume of carbon fiber and resin) and the existence of remaining elements of CaCl_2 measured by EDX, were shown in Table 1. As the solution concentrations increased, the resin amounts increased. However, even when we used 7.5% solution, the resin amount was just 30vol%, and it's not enough to make composite by only itself. So that, the additional resin films were needed to compensate.

In this method, methanol was volatilized easily by drying process, however, CaCl_2 was not removed easily because it started to separate and solidify when methanol volatilized. Therefore, if CaCl_2 separate in the deep inside of the resin it's difficult to wash it by water. As shown in EDX results, in the case of 2.5 and 5% solutions, there were no existence of the remaining elements, but in the case of 7.5% they existed inside the fabric. This means that in the case of 7.5% solution the resin layer was too thick to wash CaCl_2 by water.

From these results, the use of high concentration solution was effective to increase the resin amount in the carbon fiber fabric, but it also increased the risk that the CaCl_2 would remain in the fabric. CaCl_2 is readily soluble in water, and in that case there will be the risk that composite property decrease and Cl anion can cause the harm such as rust.

Table 1 Resin amounts and remaining solution contents in carbon fiber woven fabric by solution impregnation process with different concentrations.

Solution concentration (wt%)	Resin amount in CF fabric (vol%)	Residual solution contents
2.5	6.8	No
5.0	17.2	No
7.5	29.6	Yes

3.2 Effects of solution impregnation process on the composites quality

The effect of solution impregnation process on the composite quality was evaluated as follows. First, void contents were shown in Fig. 2. Here, the holding times of processing temperature and pressure were varied among 2.5 min, 10 min and 20 min, and the solution concentration was 5%. In the case of 2.5 min, void content by the no solution impregnation process was much higher than the one by the solution impregnation process. However, as the holding time increased, the void contents decreased, and became almost the same as the one by the solution impregnation process. Fig. 3 shows the photographs of cross sections of the composites. In the case of 2.5 min, many voids can be seen (shown as dark dots) among carbon fibers in the composite by no solution impregnation process, compared to the one by the solution impregnation process. However, as the holding time increased the voids disappeared and it showed the similar appearance as the one by the solution impregnation process.

The bending strength of the composites was shown in Fig. 4. In the case of 2.5 min, the bending strength by the solution impregnation process was almost twice larger than the one by no solution impregnation process. However, as the holding time increased, the bending strength by no solution impregnation process increased, and it reached about the same strength as the one by the solution impregnation process.

These results means that by using the solution impregnation process good impregnation quality and high bending strength could be obtained for the short compression molding time. And also, if the compression molding time is long enough, the similar composite property will be obtained by both the solution impregnation process and no solution impregnation process.

Next, a preliminary investigation for the subsequent thermoforming process was conducted. In the process, thermoplastic composite is heated, and then, pressed into a desired shape in the mold with cooling. During the heating, the resin gets melted and relaxed, which causes the appearance of many voids in the composite [5]. Fig. 5 shows the photographs of cross section of the re-heated composite. Some macro voids can be seen in resin layers in the both cases. However, micro voids inside carbon fiber bundles are hardly seen in the case of solution impregnation process, and many micro voids can be seen in the case of no solution impregnation process, although the both composite sheets before heating had showed the similar impregnation conditions. This result can be explained by the hypothesis that the amount of entrapped air solved in the resin during the compression molding process was small by replacing the air with the resin solution when the solution impregnation process was applied. And, usually micro impregnation process in carbon fiber bundles is much more difficult than macro impregnation and it's the dominating factor for total impregnation [6]. The result showed that the composite by solution impregnation process has a possible advantage to obtain better impregnation in the thermoforming process. But the further investigation will be needed to confirm it.

Fig. 2 Void of the composites using the impregnation process by PA6 solution of 5% and not using the solution with varied molding times.

Fig. 3 Cross sectional photographs of the composites (by 5% solution impregnation process and no solution impregnation process for the holding time of 2.5min and 20 min).

Fig. 4 Flexural strength of the composites (by 5% solution impregnation process and no solution impregnation process for the holding time of 2.5min, 10min and 20 min).

Fig. 5 Cross sectional photographs of the re-heated composite sheet (composites by 5% solution impregnation process and no solution impregnation process for the holding time of 20 min) .

3.3 Effects of the concentrations of solution impregnation process on the composites quality

The effect of the concentrations of the solution impregnation process on the composites quality was investigated. In this experiment, the concentrations were varied among 2.5, 5 and 7.5wt%. The holding time of processing temperature and pressure was 2.5 min for all specimens in order to emphasize the difference among them.

First, V_f and void contents of the composites were shown in Fig. 6. V_f of all the specimens were late fifties regardless of using the solution impregnation process or not. This is because the thickness of resin films were adjusted to give the same V_f as described in 2.2. The higher V_f than expected was due to the resin flow out from the mold during the compression molding process. For the void contents of the composites there was no significant difference regardless of using the different solution concentrations. If the ideal hexagonal packing of carbon fibers in the fiber bundle is considered, V_f in the fiber bundle would be 91%, that is, the cavity volume among carbon fibers would be 9% of carbon fiber bundle area. And when this value is compared to the resin amount given by the solution impregnation process (Table 1), just using 2.5% solution supposed to be enough to help the micro impregnation in this compression molding condition. And micro impregnation is the dominating factor for total impregnation as described previously.

Fig. 7 shows the photographs of the cross sections of the composites. Few voids can be seen in the cross section by the solution impregnation process. Furthermore, the thickness of resin rich layer (shown as gray areas in the middle of the photographs) became thinner and the fibers distribution became more uniform as the solution concentration increased.

Bending strength and modulus of the composites were shown in Fig. 8. There was no significant difference regardless of using the different solution concentrations. However, the strength in the case of 7.5% solution was a little higher than the cases of the other concentrations.

Fig. 6 V_f and Void of the composites (by the solution impregnation process with the solution concentrations of 2.5%, 5% and 7.5 %, and by the no solution impregnation process)

Fig. 7 Cross sectional photographs of the composites (by the solution impregnation process with the solution concentrations of 2.5%, 5% and 7.5 %, and by the no solution impregnation process)

Fig. 8 Flexural strength and flexural modulus of the composites (by the solution impregnation process with the solution concentrations of 2.5%, 5% and 7.5 %, and by the no solution impregnation process) .

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the solution impregnation process for the fabricating process of the composite sheet composed of PA6 resin and carbon fiber woven fabrics was investigated in detail. The procedure was as follows. First, carbon fiber woven fabric was impregnated with PA6 solution using the mixture of CaCl_2 and methanol, and then, those carbon fiber woven fabrics impregnated with PA6 resin and PA6 resin films were stacked up and compression moulded into composite sheet by film stacking method.

It's found that using this method, much better impregnation was obtained than in the one by not using solution impregnation process, especially when the short compression moulding time was applied. And when the moulding time was increased, the similar impregnation quality was obtained regardless of using the solution impregnation process or not.

And a preliminary investigation for thermoforming process was conducted. The cross section of composite sheet that was re-heated with no pressure was observed. It's found that micro voids were hardly seen in the one by the solution impregnation process different from many voids appearance by no solution impregnation process, and it could be the advantage for thermoforming process.

The influence of the solution concentrations on the composite quality was small in this study, and enough impregnation quality was obtained even when 2.5% solution was applied. The result suggested that the resin amount in carbon fiber woven fabric given by even 2.5% solution impregnation process would be enough to help the micro impregnation of carbon fiber bundles. And, as the solution concentration increased, the resin amount given by the solution impregnation process became high. However, it increased the possibility to cause the risk that CaCl_2 would remain inside the composite.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported by COI program "Construction of Next-generation Infrastructure System Using Innovative Composite Materials: Enabling Society to Coexist with Earth for Centuries in Safety and Security" by JST and "Regional Innovation Strategy Support Program" by MEXT.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Ben, H. Ozeki, K. Nakamura, N. Hirayama, M. Namaizawa, M. Kobayasi and H Azuma, Mechanical properties and molding conditions of CFRTP composed of carbon fabrics and In-Situ polymerized thermoplastic resin, *J. Jpn. Soc. Compos. Mater.*, **39**, 2013, pp. 127-134.
- [2] M.D. Wakeman, L. Zingraff, P.E. Bourban, J.A.E. Manson and P. Blanchard, Stamp forming of carbon fiber/PA12 composites-A comparison of a reactive impregnation process and a commingled yarn system, *Composites Science and Technology*, **66**, 2006, pp. 19-35.

- [3] M. Hattori, M. Saito, K. Okajima and K. Kamide, Molecular characterization of nylon6,6 and its dissolved state in mixture of calcium chloride and methanol, *Polymer Journal*, **27**, 1995, pp. 631-644.
- [4] O. Ishida, W. Okumura, H. Saito, M. Kimizu, K. Uzawa and I. Kimpara, Production study of carbon fiber/PA6 composite using solution of PA6, *Proceedings of JISSE conference*, 2013.
- [5] M.D. Wakeman, P.Blanchard and J.A.E. Manson, Void evolution during stamp forming of the thermoplastic composites, *ICCM-15*, 2005.
- [6] C. Mayer, X. Wang and M. Neitzel, Macro- and micro- impregnation phenomena in continuous manufacturing of fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites, *Composites Part A*, 29A, 1998, pp. 783-793.